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**D1.5 – Set of novel QSAR
models/grouping/read-across and in vitro bioassay approaches
predicting relevant toxicological endpoints for PFAS/iPM(T)
chemicals**

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Executive Summary

The deliverable is a profiling of activities for pre-selected single and complex industrial mixtures of PFAS/industrial persistent, mobile and potentially toxic pollutants iPM(T) with in vitro bioassay testing and QSAR modeling for a selection of most relevant toxicological endpoints. A set of novel in silico and in vitro methods have been developed and applied for the large group of PFAS/iPM(T)s.

The in vitro toxicity profiling followed a **stepwise approach**, by first testing the potential reference compounds PFOA and PFOS as well as industrial compounds (e.g., GenX and ADONA) with a wide range of in silico and in vitro methods (see for an overview in Annex, Table A1). Based on these initial results, the most suitable in vitro toxicity endpoints (table 7 and table 10) have been chosen for toxicity profiling the wider set of the selected PFAS compounds as well as for toxicity testing selected complex mixture (e.g., water, soil).

In the case of PMTs, at first, the potential bioactivity of several key iPM(T) (e.g., bisphenol A, triclosan, methyl-paraben, 5-chlorobenzotriazole, benzothiazole) have been evaluated using a range of in vitro toxicity profiling methods (see for an overview in Annex, Table A1). In a second step, the most suitable in vitro toxicity endpoints (table 8 and 11) have been used for toxicity profiling an extended group of iPM(T) compounds as well as for testing complex matrices (e.g., water, soil).

Regarding the group of PFAS, in silico modelling has been performed for a few thousands of chemicals (Kowalski et al., 2023), while in case of in vitro testing the focus was on a selection of 40/2 PFAS/industrial mixtures compounds proposed by the chemical-analytical laboratories involved in PROMISCES and commercially available within a limited budget.

In this study, the **in silico modeling** part investigated PFAS binding potencies to nuclear hormone receptors (NHRs) such as peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs) α , β , and γ and thyroid hormone receptors (TRs) α and β . In the first in silico step, the developed QSAR models were implemented for the screening approach of a large group of compounds (4464) from the NORMAN Database related to these 5 above mentioned NHRs. The in silico analyses indicated that the probability of PFAS binding to the receptors depends on the chain length, the number of fluorine atoms, and the number of branches in the molecule. According to the findings, the considered PFAS group bind to the PPAR α , β , and γ only with low or moderate probability, while in the case of TR α and β it is similar except that those chemicals with longer chains show a moderately high probability of binding.

The in silico analysis shows from the here tested 15 endpoints that most PFAS reflect a high binding probability to sex hormone receptors (anti-AR and ER). However, receptors from the peroxisome proliferator-activated (PPAR α , β , γ) glucocorticoid (GR and anti-GR), liver X (LXR α , β) and retinoid X (RXR α) groups are unaffected or slightly affected by PFAS (low and moderate binding probability).

Regarding the parallel **in vitro bioassay toxicity analysis**, an established standardised in vitro test battery (consisting of e.g., genotoxicity, neurotoxicity, cytotoxicity, obesity and early warning testing) was applied to meet specific criteria of PFAS/iPM(T) (endpoints, sensitivity and specificity).

Based on existing and improved CALUX bioassays, different toxicological endpoints involving metabolic syndrome (obesity related PPAR), endocrine EATS testing, genotoxicity (p53 related) and general toxicity pathways (e.g. early warning PXR) to characterise iPM(T) properties of chemicals were assessed.

The in vitro bioassay groups addressed 40 PFAS compounds (including all regulated 20 PFAS) and industrial standards (e.g., ADONA, HFPO-DA (GenX[®]) with a combination of a wide range of CALUX

bioassay endpoints (e.g., table 7 with 6 endpoints) and additional general toxicity in vitro bioassays (e.g., table 9 with 8 in vitro endpoints).

Potency factors for selected PFAS/ iPM(T) have been established for several in vitro bioassays by two laboratories involved in the project (UBA, BDS). Comparing both data sets, 80% of the relative potency factors for PFAS tested on e.g., the TTR-TR β CALUX, were found to be within an order of magnitude.

Potency factors for selected PFAS have been established. For example, in case of the TTR-TR β CALUX bioassay, the RPF values are rung from non-detected compounds (e.g., several FTOH compounds) to the perfluoro-3,7-dimethyloctanoic acid (P37DMOA) compound (RPF = up to 2.3; see tables 7 and 10).

In a second step, the 3 most active PFAS compounds on the in vitro TTR-TR β CALUX (PFOA with RPF = 1; P37DMOA with RPF = 2.3; 6:2 FTAB with RPF = 0.00015; see table 7) have been used to find in in silico modelling new **PFAS structure-analogue compounds**. In case of PFOA 12 structure-in vitro toxicity analogues were found, while in case of P37DMOA only 3 analogues and in case of 6:2 FTAB only 7 analogues were found.

Additional up to 22 iPM(T) chemicals (e.g., table 8 and 10) have been tested with a combination of a wide range of CALUX bioassays (e.g., table 8 with 6 endpoints) and additional general toxicity in vitro bioassays (e.g., table 10 with 4 in vitro endpoints). This included i) selecting a wide range of reporter gene assays to screen the toxic profiles of a set of iPM(T) chemicals, ii) selecting the most suitable bioassay panel, and iii) validating bioassay panels and cross-validating the responses obtained from the selected panel of human cell-line based bioassays.

Potency factors for selected iPM(T) have been established for each of the used in vitro human cell-based CALUX bioassays. For all CALUX bioassays applied, RPF-values ranged from not-detected (e.g., several in vitro endpoints at benzotriazole) up to RPF values above 0.5 for several iPM(T) (e.g., galaxolide and triclosan, see table 8, or methyl-paraben in table 10 at the male hormone inhibition).

Our study shows that such a **combined approach of in silico and in vitro toxicity** evaluations of single PFAS congeners (from the large group of PFAS) is a promising and suitable strategy to cover a large variety of different key events in toxicology in a time- and cost-efficient way. Such early key events can lead to protein production or molecular signalling that occur in individual cells. Later events can include altered tissue or organ function. Later and early key events are important because after the molecular later and early event, they can characterize the progression of the toxicity.

Relative potency factors (RPFs) have been determined by a combination of in silico and vitro toxicity tools and can further help to give first toxicity indications for the handful regulated and the not yet regularly tested/regulated PFAS and iPM(T) to be included in the testing strategy for single compounds and complex mixtures of these compounds.

List of Abbreviations

anti-AR	Androgen receptor antagonist
anti-ER α	Estrogen receptor alpha antagonist
anti-ER β	Estrogen receptor beta antagonist
anti-GR	Glucocorticoid receptor antagonist
AR	Androgen receptor
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
CALUX	Chemically activated luciferase gene expression
ER α	Estrogen receptor alpha
ER β	Estrogen receptor beta
GR	Glucocorticoid receptor
GSH	Glutathione
iPM(T)	industrial persistent, mobile and potentially toxic pollutants
LXR α	Liver X receptor alpha
LXR β	Liver X receptor beta
MR	Mineral corticoid receptor
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoralkyl substances
PMT	Persistent, mobile and toxic substances
PPAR α	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha
PPAR β	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor beta
PPAR γ	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma
PR	Progesterone receptor
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
RPF	Relative potency factor
RTCA	Real-time cell analysis
RXR α	Retinoid X receptor alpha
TR α	Thyroid hormone receptor alpha
TR β	Thyroid hormone receptor beta
TTR	Transthyretin

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1 Set of novel QSAR models/grouping/read-across approaches predicting relevant toxicological endpoints for PFAS/iPM(T) chemicals for QSAR modelling for PFAS

1.1 Introduction

Improved in vitro and in silico methodologies for toxicological assessment of environmental media/drinking water and regulatory tools, is evaluated in this report

The current knowledge gap and objective of our work is to profile activities for single compounds and complex mixtures of pre-selected PFAS/iPM(T)s by developing suitable in vitro/QSAR methods. Such in silico and in vitro toxicity profiles of the selected PFAS/iPM(T)s are not developed/published yet and will help to select the most relevant in silico and in vitro toxicological endpoints.

Aim of this deliverable is to improve in vitro testing strategies and established a methodology combining in silico toxicology and in vitro testing in order to provide a set of toxicological assessment and regulatory tools for PFAS/PM(T) chemicals.

Deliverable 1.5. directly relates to the objective of Task 1.3 which is to develop or/and improve in vitro testing strategies and to establish a methodology combining in silico toxicology and in vitro testing in order to provide a set of toxicological assessment and regulatory tools.

Expected goal of this deliverable is to establish a set of novel QSAR/grouping/read-across models and in vitro bioassay approaches predicting relevant toxicological endpoints for PFAS/iPM(T) chemicals. Each QSAR model included a structural property of the molecule describing its size/branching and one that described the content of fluorine in the molecule expressed (i) directly by the number of fluorine atoms (nF) or (ii) indirectly by the percentage of halogens (%X) or average molar weight (AMW). The developed QSAR models predict binding probability to different receptors which can be analysed by the here used in vitro toxicity panel.

Our aim is to confirm that first indications in published literature **from a few PFAS compounds in in silico modeling** (e.g., Yu et al., 2022) is that many PFAS reflect a high binding probability to sex hormone receptors (anti-AR and ER), as well as receptors from the peroxisome proliferator-activated (PPAR α , β , γ) glucocorticoid (GR and anti-GR), liver X (LXR α , β) and retinoid X (RXR α) groups are unaffected or slightly affected by PFAS.

With respect to **in silico modelling**, our aim is to confirm that high binding probability to sex hormone receptors (anti-AR, ER α , TR β), receptors for peroxisome proliferation (PPAR α , β , γ), glucocorticoid receptor (GR and anti-GR), liver X receptors (LXR α , β) and retinoid X receptor (RXR α) is not limited to a small number of PFAS compounds (so far published e.g., Yu et al., 2022), but rather applies to a wider range of PFAS.

With respect to **in vitro bioanalysis**, our aim is to evaluate whether published information on endocrine disruption by a few tested PFAS (e.g., estrogen-, androgen-, thyroid-disruption by Young et al., 2021) can also be applied on a wider range of PFAS compounds.

Relative potency factors (RPFs) received by a combination of in silico and in vitro toxicity tools can help to give first toxicity indications for the handful regulated and the not yet regularly tested/regulated PFAS to be included in the testing strategy and further risk assessment.

Potency factors for selected PFAS/ iPM(T) will be analysed by two independent in vitro laboratories from the PROMISCES consortium (UBA, BDS) by using several CALUX bioassays (e.g., TTR TR β CALUX).

The **impact** of the combination of in silico and vitro toxicity evaluations of single PFAS congeners from the large group of PFAS is a promising and suitable strategy to cover a large variety of different key events in a time- and cost-efficient way.

Also, structure-toxicity analogues of new PFAS will be described in the in-silico modeling part of this report

1.2 QSAR models development for the binding score (BS) to Nuclear Hormone Receptors (NHRs) for PFAS

Within this task QSAR Lab developed a total of 16 models for predicting the binding score (BS) value to nuclear hormone receptors for PFAS. Specifically, there were 12 different Nuclear Hormone Receptors (NHRs) with up to an additional four antagonistic conformations (PPAR α , PPAR β , PPAR γ , TR α , TR β , RXR α , LXR α , LXR β , GR, anti-GR, AR, anti-AR, ER α , anti-ER α , ER β , anti-ER β) (Table 1). The Endocrine Disruptome (ED) tool was used to include a total of 14 receptors. But 2 of them were identified by the authors as having a very poor performance of around 50%. For this reason, PR and MR were not included in our study. Data on BS to be used as input for QSAR modeling was generated using the open-source ED tool (<https://doi.org/10.1021/ci400649p>).

The set of 43 compounds we used for analysis was a modified data set previously published for prediction in the ED tool (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.133366>). This set has been applied because of its appropriate diversity yet simplicity. It included, among others, a PFAS group with a carboxyl or sulfonic group where the compounds differed in their subsequent CF₂ groups. Such use of a set of compounds allows more efficient identification of structural features affecting the activity of the molecule under study. The modification of the original literature dataset (from 49 to 43 compounds) was due to the presence of compounds above 600 g/mol, as the authors of the tool indicated this as a limitation that could lead to incorrect results.

1.2.1 MLR (Multiple Linear Regression)-QSAR modelling methodology

Data generation: Data were generated using the ED Tool where molecules were implemented using SMILES notation, and then binding score values were obtained from docking in AutoDock Vina. The data for 43 commonly used PFAS (Annex Table A2) were obtained and then used to build the QSAR model. An additional functionality of the Endocrine Disruptome tool is to assign the value of the obtained binding energy to four classes taking into account the probability of binding. The class with the lowest binding probability, followed by second with moderate binding probability, then third with moderately high binding probability, and last fourth with a high probability of binding to the NHRs. The probability classes were not used in the development of MLR-QSAR models but were considered in further analysis to screening the huge set of PFAS compounds.

Descriptors: The input data for modeling were molecular descriptors calculated using AlvaDesc software, for entire analyzed group of 43 most common PFAS, describing a total of 4 selected groups (constitutional indices, topological indices, walk and path counts, and molecular properties) comprising a final 186 1D and 2D molecular descriptors. Each model (MLR-QSPR predictive model) was based on 2 molecular descriptors whose correlation in the training set of the model didn't exceed 0.6. A total of 9 different descriptors used in various combinations were used. In general terms, it can be concluded that each MLR-QSPR model included a structural property of the molecule

explaining/describing its size/branching and one that described the content of fluorine atoms in the molecule expressed directly by the number of fluorine atoms (nF) or indirectly by the percentage of halogens (%X) or average molar weight (AMW).

1.2.2 QSAR modeling

Data set for 43 PFAS (i.e., perfluorinated sulfonic acids (PFASs), fluorotelomer alcohols (FTOHs), perfluorinated carboxylic acids (PFCAs), perfluorinated phosphonic acids (PFPA), and others, see for an overview in Annex Table A2) were used to develop MLR-QSAR models. The endpoint values were the BS calculated with the ED tool, and the set of 186 descriptors was the input for selection-assisted modeling through genetic algorithm (GA). A GA was implemented to appropriately select the variables in the modeling (descriptors), taking into account the division of the compounds between the training (T) and validation set (V). To split our dataset we used the '1:Z' algorithm which means that compounds sorted according to increasing binding score were divided in such a way, that each Zth compound was assigned to a validation set and the rest of the molecules created a training set. Whereas in each QSAR-model the first and last compound (with the lowest and highest energy) enters the training set so that it reflects the entire span of the data set used, and the validation set is within the limits of applicability of the model. In our case, we applied the '1:Z' algorithm where (i) Z=3 for PPAR α , PPAR β , TR β RXR α , LXR α , LXR β , GR, anti-GR, AR, anti-AR, ER β , anti-ER β , and (ii) Z=4 for PPAR γ , TR α , ER α , anti-ER α where 29 or 33 PFAS were assigned to the training set respectively.

Determining factors to model selection: Models selection was based on:

- (i) a mechanistic approach due to a narrowed group of descriptors to 1D and 2D which considered chosen properties (descriptors within 4 different groups described above) of analyzed compounds and
- (ii) a statistical approach using the received statistics of QSAR-models based on the previously mentioned GA. The equations of the obtained selected QSAR-models are shown in Table 1 and the exact statistics of all models are shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Scheme 1. Diagram showing the 4 main steps of the analysis carried out.

As a measure of the goodness of fit (the ability of the QSAR models to reproduce the compounds in the training set) we calculated the R^2 (squared regression coefficient) and the $RMSE_c$ (root mean square error of calibration). The R^2 should be close to 1; in our models the R^2 was higher than 0.9 in 14 out of 16 cases. The two cases with a lower value were for AR and anti-AR models (0.827 and 0.897 respectively). To evaluate the predictivity and robustness of the model, we conducted an internal validation¹ as well as an external validation²). We also obtained $R^2_{Y_{SCR}}$ from an R^2 averaging for 100 random models (based on the same descriptors) to check that the obtained model is well established. This allows to avoid the model obtained by chance. In all cases $R^2_{Y_{SCR}}$ was lower than 0.08.

The evaluation of the developed models was based not only on the statistics obtained but also on the evaluation of the prepared graph. One of them is a graph of the relationship between the observed (calculated) values versus predicted values. This graphical presentation further helps to determine whether the coefficient of fit (R^2) was not obtained by chance such as equating results that were strongly overestimated or underestimated. The better the fit of the position of the points on the line, the better the correlation of the obtained predictions with the experimental (calculated) data. An illustration of these results for each developed model is shown in Figures 1-5 (A, C, E, G).

¹ training set: cross-validation coefficient (Q^2_{LOO}), the root means square error of cross-validation ($RMSE_{CV}$), mean absolute error (MAE_{CV})

² validation set; external validation coefficients (Q_{F1}^2 , Q_{F2}^2 , Q_{F3}^2), root mean square error ($RMSE_{EXT}$), mean absolute error (MAE_{EXT}), and concordance correlation coefficient (CCC_{EXT})

Table 1: Models equations for the binding score (BS) to the nuclear hormone receptors PPAR α , PPAR β , PPAR γ , TR α , TR β , RXR α , LXR α , LXR β , GR, anti-GR, AR, anti-AR, ER α , anti-ER α , ER β , anti-ER β .

Model	Equation
PPAR α	PPAR α BS = $-7.499 (\pm 0.067) - 0.947 (\pm 0.070) \times \text{ICR} - 0.394 (\pm 0.070) \times \text{PW2}$
PPAR β	PPAR β BS = $-8.248 (\pm 0.069) - 1.059 (\pm 0.071) \times \text{ICR} - 0.409 (\pm 0.071) \times \text{X}\%$
PPAR γ	PPAR γ BS = $-7.727 (\pm 0.052) - 1.099 (\pm 0.053) \times \text{ICR} - 0.398 (\pm 0.053) \times \text{X}\%$
TR α	TR α BS = $-8.230 (\pm 0.070) - 1.189 (\pm 0.071) \times \text{ICR} - 0.454 (\pm 0.071) \times \text{X}\%$
TR β	TR β BS = $-8.724 (\pm 0.054) - 1.509 (\pm 0.061) \times \text{TPC} - 0.137 (\pm 0.061) \times \text{X}\%$
RXR α	RXR α BS = $-8.869 (\pm 0.061) - 1.293 (\pm 0.069) \times \text{MWC02} - 0.263 (\pm 0.069) \times \text{X}\%$
LXR α	LXR α BS = $-8.803 (\pm 0.062) - 1.459 (\pm 0.071) \times \text{TPC} - 0.178 (\pm 0.071) \times \text{X}\%$
LXR β	LXR β BS = $-8.462 (\pm 0.038) - 1.430 (\pm 0.04) \times \text{TPC} - 0.175 (\pm 0.04) \times \text{X}\%$
GR	GR BS = $-7.759 (\pm 0.064) - 0.182 (\pm 0.067) \times \text{PW2} + 1.176 (\pm 0.067) \times \text{ESOL}$
anti - GR	anti-GR BS = $-7.017 (\pm 0.043) - 0.859 (\pm 0.048) \times \text{MWC02} - 0.1942 (\pm 0.048) \times \text{X}\%$
AR	AR BS = $-8.728 (\pm 0.093) - 0.847 (\pm 0.104) \times \text{piPC06} - 0.325 (\pm 0.104) \times \text{X}\%$
anti-AR	anti-AR BS = $-8.569 (\pm 0.075) - 1.131 (\pm 0.076) \times \text{TPC} - 0.255 (\pm 0.076) \times \text{AMW}$
ER α	ER α BS = $-8.042 (\pm 0.038) - 1.35 (\pm 0.042) \times \text{TPC} - 0.205 (\pm 0.042) \times \text{X}\%$
anti-ER α	anti-ER α BS = $-8.048 (\pm 0.044) - 1.302 (\pm 0.047) \times \text{TPC} - 0.298 (\pm 0.047) \times \text{X}\%$
ER β	ER β BS = $-8.538 (\pm 0.063) - 1.362 (\pm 0.072) \times \text{MWC02} - 0.201 (\pm 0.072) \times \text{X}\%$
anti-ER β	anti-ER β BS = $-8.069 (\pm 0.083) - 1.150 (\pm 0.091) \times \text{nF} - 0.370 (\pm 0.091) \times \text{PW2}$

Descriptors used in equations: **ICR** – radial centric information index; **X%** – a percentage of halogen atoms; **MWC02** – molecular walk count of order 2; **TPC** – total path count; **ESOL** – Estimated Solubility (logS) for aqueous solubility using LOGPcons; **PW2** – path/walk 2 – Randic shape index; **piPC06** – molecular multiple path count of order 6; **AMW** – average molecular weight; **nF** – number of fluorine atoms.

Table 2: Statistical parameters for PPAR α , PPAR β , PPAR γ , TR α , TR β , RXR α , LXR α , and β (n: number of PFAS in training set, k: number of PFAS invalidation set).

Model	PPAR α	PPAR β	PPAR γ	TR α	TR β	RXR α	LXR α	LXR β
n	29	29	33	33	29	29	29	29
k	14	14	10	10	14	14	14	14
R²	0.917	0.924	0.949	0.924	0.970	0.955	0.960	0.984
RMSE_c	0.341	0.352	0.287	0.384	0.276	0.311	0.317	0.192
MAE_c	0.288	0.272	0.201	0.327	0.221	0.229	0.259	0.158
Q²_{Loo}	0.878	0.903	0.940	0.908	0.955	0.927	0.938	0.978
RMSE_{cv}	0.350	0.398	0.310	0.422	0.340	0.396	0.395	0.224
MAE_{cv}	0.244	0.304	0.219	0.360	0.256	0.269	0.302	0.179
Q²_{F1}	0.897	0.917	0.907	0.899	0.948	0.941	0.951	0.960
Q²_{F2}	0.897	0.916	0.906	0.899	0.947	0.941	0.951	0.960
Q²_{F3}	0.912	0.922	0.952	0.934	0.954	0.950	0.956	0.966
RMSE_{EXT}	0.352	0.359	0.279	0.359	0.344	0.328	0.333	0.278
MAE_{EXT}	0.257	0.279	0.223	0.312	0.280	0.258	0.284	0.21
CCC_{EXT}	0.937	0.952	0.953	0.946	0.973	0.967	0.976	0.979
R²_{SCR}	0.070	0.068	0.062	0.061	0.070	0.071	0.072	0.738

Table 3: Statistical parameters for GR, anti-GR, AR, anti-AR, ER α , anti-ER α , ER β , and anti-ER β models (n: number of PFAS in training set, k: number of PFAS invalidation set).

Model	GR	anti-GR	AR	anti-AR	ER α	anti-ERα	ER β	anti-ERβ
n	29	29	29	29	33	33	29	29
k	14	14	14	14	10	10	14	14
R²	0.937	0.949	0.827	0.897	0.98	0.973	0.953	0.911
RMSE_C	0.322	0.223	0.474	0.382	0.206	0.244	0.325	0.420
MAE_C	0.252	0.178	0.391	0.279	0.155	0.189	0.258	0.326
Q²_{LOO}	0.921	0.938	0.766	0.874	0.972	0.965	0.923	0.887
RMSE_{CV}	0.362	0.245	0.550	0.421	0.247	0.271	0.417	0.473
MAE_{CV}	0.283	0.197	0.449	0.307	0.177	0.211	0.307	0.368
Q²_{F1}	0.936	0.905	0.826	0.842	0.983	0.973	0.950	0.905
Q²_{F2}	0.934	0.905	0.826	0.842	0.983	0.973	0.950	0.905
Q²_{F3}	0.943	0.934	0.869	0.883	0.989	0.983	0.950	0.914
RMSE_{EXT}	0.308	0.254	0.412	0.408	0.148	0.188	0.323	0.414
MAE_{EXT}	0.243	0.213	0.232	0.300	0.118	0.157	0.227	0.330
CCC_{EXT}	0.966	0.953	0.921	0.925	0.991	0.985	0.973	0.950
R²_{SCR}	0.074	0.074	0.070	0.070	0.061	0.062	0.071	0.072

Figure 1: Plot of observed versus predicted values of binding scores for PPAR α , PPAR β , PPAR γ , and TR α (A, C, E, G respectively). William's plot: dash line indicates the critical leverage value, solid lines represent $\pm 3\sigma$, standard deviation units. (B, D, F, H respectively).

Figure 2: Plot of observed versus predicted values of binding scores for TR α , RXR α , LXR α , and LXR β (A, C, E, G respectively). William's plot: dash line indicates the critical leverage value, solid lines represent $\pm 3\sigma$, standard deviation units. (B, D, F, H respectively).

Figure 3: Plots of observed versus predicted values of binding scores for GR, GR antagonist, AR, and AR antagonist (A, C, E, G respectively). Williams plots: dash line indicates the critical leverage value, solid lines represent $\pm 3\sigma$, standard deviation units. (B, D, F, H respectively).

Figure 4: Plots of observed versus predicted values of binding scores for ER α , ER α antagonist, ER β , ER β antagonist (A, C, E, G respectively). Williams plots: dash line indicates the critical leverage value, solid lines represent $\pm 3\sigma$, standard deviation units. (B, D, F, H respectively).

Subsequently, the applicability domain (AD) of the models was checked using a graphical representation: Williams plot. The AD is defined as the chemical space where the compounds are considered similar to the training set. The Y-axis describes ± 3 standard deviations from the mean value while the x-axis gives the critical leverage (\hat{h}) value, which depends on the number of compounds in the training set.

Based on this analysis, which is illustrated in Figures 2-5 (B, D, F, H), it can be seen that the compound most frequently considered as an outlier was compound 43 (TFA), which exceeded the critical leverage value for 15 of the 16 (all except the MLR-QSAR model for AR) models developed. In addition, compounds 16 (EtFOSE) and 23 (PFBA) occurred as outliers once (in the model for LXR α and the one for AR, respectively). If the leverage value for the compound is higher than the critical value (and not exceeding ± 3 standard deviations from the mean value), this means that the predicted response can only be extrapolated from the model with great care. The results show that values exceeding the critical leverage value are compounds differing in structure from the set used to develop the model. Here, compound 43 (TFA) is an ideal example: There were several carboxylic acids in the training set that are fully substituted with fluorine. TFA is the smallest molecule among them, deviating based on topological descriptors. Only in the case of one model (MLR-QSAR for AR) was this compound not treated as an outlier. This is because the topological descriptor differentiates molecules over a longer distance, so TFA was not different from those that contained a few more CF₂ groups in the chain. In addition, the calculated descriptors preserved the 'ratio' that can be seen in the rest of the molecules: molecules with a longer main chain have a greater number of fluorine atoms, that is, usually the chain is extended by another CF₂ group. For PFBA, piPC06 was still equal to 0 (same as TFA) despite 4 atoms in the main chain and the X% value was already at 50 making it significantly different from the other compounds resulting in its classification as an outlier.

Figure 5 Structures of compounds classified as outliers among all developed MLR-QSAR models

In order to gain additional knowledge on the possible consequences of PFAS binding to NHRs, further scientific studies are needed, mainly based on a deeper characterization of the exact binding sites of PFAS to receptors. However, the presented results suggest that the pathways mediated by the studied receptors should be considered when studying the toxicity mechanisms of PFAS.

There are several experimental studies in the literature describing the effect of PFAS on NHRs. However, it is not possible to directly compare the reported results due to differences in the measurement technique used, the test conditions, or the cell line selected. On the other hand, most

of these studies confirmed the influence of the characteristics described by the selected descriptors on PFAS-receptor binding strength (size, presence of branching, substitution of carbons by fluorine).

The biological test results found in the literature agreed in trend with the docking results we obtained, a direct comparison between the two is not possible because the probability of PFAS binding to receptors depends on the specificity of ligand binding pocket (LBD - the place, where PFAS fit into).

A detailed description of 5 (PPAR α , PPAR β , PPAR γ , TR α , TR β) of the 14 developed QSAR-models including the individual interpretation and prediction ability has been published in *Molecules* (<https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28020479>). For the remaining 11 developed models (RXR α , LXR α , LXR β , GR, anti-GR, AR, anti-AR, ER α , anti-ER α , ER β , anti-ER β), a manuscript is in the revision step in *Chemosphere*, including a broader interpretation of the results obtained.

1.3 Clustering of a large PFAS database

INERIS carried out unsupervised learning³ aimed at a clustering a large database of PFAS in order to map experimental *in vitro* data generated by the project (partner BDS) within the chemical space covered by PFAS. The purpose of clustering can be summarized according to the following logic:

- A large pool of PFAS is organized by means of unsupervised learning in clusters. PFAS belonging to the same cluster are structurally similar. Structural similarity is measured by means of molecular descriptors and fingerprints.
- Original *in vitro* data generated by the project is superposed to the clusters.
- The untested PFAS contained within clusters where PFAS characterized by high Relative Potency Factors (RPF) are mapped, could be prioritized for testing.
- Experimentally tested PFAS, regardless of their RPF, can be considered as “source chemicals” for implementing read-across predictions within the clusters they belong to. Indeed, predictions by read-across are realized by using experimental data associated with “source chemicals” to predict experimentally untested target chemicals that are considered to be structurally similar to the source chemicals (Berggren et al., 2015). In the simplest case, the experimental activity characterizing source chemicals is simply transposed toward untested chemicals. In other cases, the biological activity for query PFAS could be, for instance, be estimated by adopting the mean experimental activity characterizing source chemicals.

1.3.1 Methods for clustering

- Chemical structures corresponding to 12654 unique PFAS (the largest available inventory of PFAS) described in Richard et al. (Richard et al., 2023) were retrieved and normalized according to the workflow proposed by Gadaleta (Gadaleta et al., 2018a).

³ Unsupervised learning is a machine-learning approach that can distinguish patterns within data that are not easy to be detected by visual inspection. This approach does not rely on labelled data such as, for instance, the distinction between active or inactive chemicals with respect to a biological target.

- Freely available 2D Mordred Molecular descriptors (Moriwaki et al., 2018) were computed and used alongside freely available fingerprints especially developed for PFAS (Richard et al., 2023). The final number of molecular descriptors/fingerprints used for describing chemical structures was equal to 1130.

- Partition Around Medoids was used as clustering algorithm (Wehrens, 2011). The optimal number of clusters was determined by maximising the average silhouette score. Silhouette scores range from -1 to +1. Scores close to +1 indicate an optimal assignment of PFAS to their clusters. This stratagem was used in order to remove arbitrariness when selecting the optimal number of clusters and it optimizes the cohesion and separation of clusters at the same time (Wehrens, 2011). Distances (i.e., dissimilarities) among chemicals were computed according to Gower distance which can handle mixed data {Giordani, 2020 #2091} such as the one provided by molecular descriptors and fingerprints (nominal data).

1.3.2 Clustering results

The clustering algorithm resulted in more than 4000 clusters. The *in vitro* RPF-values that were experimentally characterized for 35 PFAS by partner BDS by conducting the *in vitro* human cell-based TTR-TR β CALUX assay (thyroid hormone transport disruption), belong to thirty-two not overlapping clusters comprising 158 other PFAS.

6, 7 and 8 permit the visualization of clusters for three typical PFAS showing a high (P37DMOA, RPF_{TTR} = 2.3), medium (PFOA, RPF_{TTR} = 1) and low *in vitro* RPF (6:2 FTAB, RPF_{TTR} = 0.00015). The visual inspection of these clusters highlights the elevated level of structural homogeneity of its members. This structural homogeneity is a prerequisite for carrying out read-across predictions.

PFAS clustering with P37DMOA could be prioritized for testing giving their potential high *in vitro* RPF.

Figure 6. Cluster analysis indicated that P37DMOA (the PFAS characterized by the highest *in vitro* RPF) is contained within a group composed by four PFAS that are characterized by a similar chemical structure and chemical topology (i.e. two-dimensional arrangement of atoms). Cluster analysis was carried out as a function of 1130 molecular descriptors/fingerprints and dissimilarities among chemicals were measured by the Gower Distance.

Figure 7. Cluster analysis indicated that 6:2 FTAB (the PFAS with the lowest *in vitro* RPF) is contained within a group composed by eight PFAS that are characterized by a similar chemical structure and chemical topology (i.e. two-dimensional arrangement of atoms). Cluster analysis was carried out as a function of 1130 molecular descriptors/fingerprints and dissimilarities among chemicals were measured by the Gower Distance.

1.4 QSAR modelling for Industrial Persistent and Mobile PM(T) toxicants

INERIS developed QSAR models for industrial persistent and mobile iPM(T) chemicals for nuclear receptors of interest for the project. The modelled biological activity corresponded to positive and negative hit-calls (i.e., active and inactive chemicals in cell-based assays) as yielded by the ToxCast program {EPA, 2022 #2051}{Dix, 2007 #489}. Since the QSAR models classify chemicals in two classes “inactive” vs “active”, they will be referred to as “QSAR classifiers”.

A positive hit-call is a perturbation having a maximum median response that exceeds a specific cut-off that characterizes the cell-based assay and whose data points can be fit to a dose-response curve. The selected receptors are listed in the Annex in Table A1. Research of experimental data was focused on the ToxCast database since it includes human cell-based assays together with information on cytotoxicity (essential information in order to avoid false positive responses of the nuclear receptor assays). This database was intersected with the list of iPM(T) chemicals published by the UBA (UBA, 2021) and by the Danish Technical University (Holmberg et al., 2021) (811 chemicals 52 of which are PFAS) in order to focus the development of QSAR classifiers on PM chemicals.

PFOA

$$RPF_{TTR} = 1$$

Figure 8. Cluster analysis indicated that PFOA (the reference chemical for *in vitro* RPF) is contained within a group composed by 13 PFAS that are characterized by a similar chemical structure and chemical topology (i.e. two-dimensional arrangement of atoms). Cluster analysis was carried out as a function of 1130 molecular descriptors/fingerprints and dissimilarities among chemicals were measured by the Gower Distance. PFOA including isotopes are labelled with a star.

As Figure 9 shows that sufficient data for active chemicals devoid of cytotoxic effects were only present for the Estrogen Receptor (ER), Pregnane X receptor (PXR), and the Nuclear factor (erythroid-derived 2)-like 2 (NRF2). There is no general agreement with respect to the exact extent of class imbalance that impairs machine learning regardless of the algorithms used to artificially balance the data. Nevertheless, two aspects have to be considered: the Imbalance Ratio⁴ (IR) and the number of instances belonging to the minority class. Datasets that are characterized by an IR ranging from 4 to 20 are generally considered as high {Hakim, 2022 #2092} and therefore difficult to be modelled. In addition, the number of instances belonging to the minority class must also be provide to machine learning algorithms a sufficient number of instances that can result into a model capable of generalizing what learnt. Indeed, a dataset characterized by a moderate IR but with an insufficient number of chemicals (less than 15 in the framework of this work) in the minority class will be biased

⁴ The sample size of the majority class (i.e., active chemicals) divided by the sample size of the minority class.

towards an improper validation. As a matter of fact, chemicals must also be present in the validation set, reducing therefore the available information used during calibration and the memorization of the structural features characterizing the minority class instead of the ability to generalize predictions towards unseen chemicals.

9 and 10 show that only PXR, Nrf2 and ER meet the conditions for developing QSAR models able to generalize. Therefore, QSAR development was focused on these three targets.

Figure 9. Number of active chemicals for PM chemicals present in the ToxCast assays for the endpoints of interest. Androgen Receptor antagonism (black bars), Estrogen Receptor (white bars), p53 (green bars), Glucocorticoid Receptor (grey bars), Pregnane X receptor (red bars), Nuclear factor (erythroid-derived 2)-like 2 (Nrf2) (cyan bars), Thyroid Receptor (magenta bars), Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptors alpha and gamma (PPAR) (green bars), orange Glucocorticoid Receptor (GR). The dotted line represents a threshold corresponding to 15 chemicals below which QSAR modelling will be based on insufficient information for learning how to discriminate active chemicals.

1.4.1 Molecular descriptors

SMILES codes normalized by the KNIME workflow proposed by Gadaleta et al. (Gadaleta et al., 2018) were used as input for the freeware Mordred v 1.2.0 (School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Osaka University, 1-6 Yamadaoka, Suita City, Osaka 565-0871, Japan). This software was used to calculate more than 1600 two-dimensional descriptors.

Figure 10. IR for the endpoints of interest. Androgen Receptor antagonism (black bars), Estrogen Receptor (white bars), p53 (green bars), Glucocorticoid Receptor (grey bars), Pregnane X receptor (red bars), Nuclear factor (erythroid-derived 2)-like 2 (Nrf2) (cyan bars), Thyroid Receptor (magenta bars), Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptors alpha and gamma (PPAR) green bars), orange Glucocorticoid Receptor (GR).

1.4.2 Balanced Random Forest (BRF) algorithm for QSAR modelling

Given the imbalanced nature of the dataset (*i.e.*, a minority of active chemicals) the Balanced Random Forest (BRF) algorithm was adopted (number of trees = 301). All the QSAR computations were carried out with the software R (version 4.2.2) (R Core Team, 2022) and the RandomForest library (Liaw and Wiener, 2002). The number of trees was equal to 301 and all the other BRF parameters were the default parameters of the RandomForest library. Applicability domain (AD)

Previous work (Gadaleta et al., 2018b) showed that useful metrics for AD definition with RF are the variability of predictions among individual RF trees (a wide variation indicates less accurate predictions) and the distance to closest neighbours (long distances indicate that a chemical is not surrounded by similar structural analogues). For this reason, in the present work, both aspects were considered for the definition of models' AD.

More specifically, the prediction concordance of the trees was considered when estimating the first criterion. The second AD criterion was formalized by building a distance matrix containing Euclidean distances for each pair of chemicals in the training set. Subsequently, for each chemical in the training set, the mean distance from its first 3 neighbours was calculated. The chemicals in the training set were then sorted on the basis of these distances, and the value corresponding to a given percentile of the distribution of distances was used as a threshold beyond which chemicals belonging to the external test set were excluded from the AD.

The adopted thresholds for these two criteria were: 0.55, 0.60, and 0.65 (for predictive concordance of trees) and 95th, 90th and 85th for the critical percentiles of Euclidean distances. The coupling of these two sets of thresholds resulted in three AD definitions of increasing stringency.

1.4.3 Design of datasets

In order to keep only molecular descriptors associated with useful information for modelling the initial set of molecular descriptors was pruned with respect to correlation among descriptors (highly correlated descriptors encode basically the same information) and with respect to the number of repeated values. This last pruning is needed since descriptors with many repeated values, if deemed useful by the modelling algorithms, will tend to overfit QSAR approaches by discriminating only a small proportion of chemicals. For this reason, a pruning threshold for correlation (correlation > 0.97) and for the proportion of repeated values (> 90% repeated values) was used to keep only potentially predictive molecular descriptors associated with non-redundant information. The initial dataset was split into a training set (75%) and an external test set (25%). The external test set adequately covers the chemical space (i.e., identification of representative chemicals by partitioning around medoids) defined by the training set and it was used solely and uniquely for evaluating the performance of the selected QSAR model. Information in the external test set was not used during calibration and model selection.

1.4.4 Model selection

Genetic algorithms (population size = 300, Cross-over probability = 0.7, mutation probability = 0.02) implemented in the R library GA (Scrucca, 2013) were used to select molecular descriptors. They adopted the Matthews's correlation coefficient (MCC) resulting from a repeated (50 times) 10-fold cross-validation applied to the training set as fitness. The MCC [-1,+1], is a reliable statistical index in the presence of imbalanced datasets since it yields a high score only if the prediction obtained good results with respect to all of the four confusion matrix categories (i.e. true positives, false negatives, true negatives, and false positives). This is done by taking into account the proportionality to the size of active chemicals and the size of inactive chemicals in the dataset (Chicco and Jurman, 2020). To prevent overfitting, the fitness was linearly penalized (slope = 0.015) if the Topliss ratio of the model went below 10. The molecular descriptors that resulted in the best fitness out of 15 GA runs were retained as predictors. During the GA iterations, no information from the external test set was used.

1.4.5 Evaluation of predictive performance

The predictive performance of the QSAR classifiers was evaluated according to the Cooper's statistics (Cooper et al., 1979): Sensitivity and Specificity. Sensitivity indicates the capacity of the model to correctly identify active chemicals and it is defined by the ratio between the number of true positives⁵ divided by the number of experimentally active chemicals), whereas specificity indicates the capacity of the model to correctly identify inactive chemicals and it is defined by the ratio between the number of true negatives⁶ divided by the number of experimentally inactive chemicals). Both indicators range from 0 to 1 (perfect model).

These statistical indicators on their own cannot completely describe the predictive performance of imbalanced datasets such as the datasets of the three aforementioned nuclear receptors since they are characterized by high IR which are defined by the ratio of inactive chemicals to the number of active chemicals. For this reason, the MCC was computed alongside Cooper's statistics.

⁵ A true positive is an experimentally active chemicals which is predicted as such by the QSAR classifiers

⁶ A true negative is an experimentally inactive chemicals which is predicted as such by the QSAR classifier

The predictive performance of *in vitro* test methods for which OECD guidelines have been published can be used to provide a generic benchmark about the usefulness of *in silico* approaches. In this respect, Misik et al. {Mišík, 2022 #1815} highlighted that the median values for indicated sensitivities and specificities characterizing OECD-endorsed *in vitro* tests for genotoxicity are 0.73 and 0.76 respectively. This benchmark is not endpoint-specific but it provides a benchmark in terms of Cooper's statistics for what can be deemed as fit for toxicological evaluation and what can be regarded as suboptimal: specificities and sensitivities that are above 0.7.

1.4.6 Conformity with the OECD validation principles for QSAR models

The developed QSAR classifier were evaluated according to the OECD validation principles for QSAR models (OCDE, 2004). Indeed, the modelled endpoint is well-defined, the algorithm is transparent and reproducible, the models have been evaluated for robustness and predictivity, an applicability domain was defined, and the molecular descriptors describe the structural arrangement of atoms within chemicals that drives the affinity of chemicals towards the modelled nuclear receptors.

1.4.7 QSAR classifier for PXR

For implementing the PXR QSAR classifier, the ToxCast endpoints 'ATG_PXR_TRANS_up' and 'ATG_PXRE_CIS_up' were merged to increase the number of chemicals to be modelled. The predictive performance of the PXR classifier is summarized in Table 4. The introduction of applicability domains of increasing stringency results in an increase in performance at the expense of reduced coverage (1).

The sensitivity and specificity of the PXR classifier can be considered as fit for the purpose of a screening of list of chemicals since sensitivity goes beyond 0.7 within the applicability domain while specificity reaches high values by approaching and exceeding 0.8. This predictive performance ensures a reduced number of false positives and a subsequent prioritization of experimental resources targeted towards chemicals very likely to display a disruption potential.

It can therefore be concluded that what the underlying structure-activity relationship of the *in vitro* tests was adequately described and that Cooper's statistics conforms to what is generally regarded as useful in regulatory contexts {Mišík, 2022 #1815}.

Table 4. Predictive performance on internal and external validation of the PXR BRF classifier. #TR = number of chemicals in the training set; #TS = number of chemicals in the test set; IR_{TR} = Imbalance Ratio training set (number of inactive chemicals/number of active chemicals); IR_{TS} = Imbalance Ratio training set; loo = leave-one-out cross-validation; Iso = leave-several-out 10-fold; MCC = Matthews's correlation coefficient; SEN = Sensitivity; SPE = specificity.

#TR	IR _{TS}	#TS	IR _{TS}	Internal Validation						External validation		
				MCC _{loo}	MCC _{Iso}	SEN _{loo}	SEN _{Iso}	SPE _{loo}	SPE _{Iso}	MCC _{EXT}	SEN _{EXT}	SPE _{EXT}
302	2.50	100	2.57	0.55	0.55	0.70	0.70	0.86	0.85	0.45	0.68	0.79

Figure 11. Effect of AD of increasing stringency (*i.e.*, increasing percentage of excluded chemicals) on the predictive performance of the PXR BRF classifier.

1.4.8 QSAR classifier for Nrf2

The Nrf2 classifier was developed as a function of data associated with the ToxCast endpoint 'ATG_NRF2_ARE_CIS_up'. The predictive performance of the Nrf2 classifier is summarized in Table 5. It appears that this classifier is characterized by a capacity to detect active chemicals (sensitivity), which is suboptimal. The introduction of an applicability domain (Figure 2) improves the trend but sensitivity reaches acceptable levels only at significantly reduced coverages but the selected structure-activity relations do not reproduce the mechanistic rationale underpinning the corresponding *in vitro* tests. Notwithstanding the suboptimal sensitivity, the high specificity of this classifier, can still be of some use for screening purposes. Indeed, it can be used to guide experimental testing in the presence of a reduced number of false positives.

Table 5. Predictive performance on internal and external validation of the Nrf2 BRF classifier; #TR = number of chemicals in training set; #TS = number of chemicals in test set; IR_{TR} = Imbalance Ratio training set (number of inactive chemicals/number of active chemicals); IR_{TS} = Imbalance Ratio training set; loo = leave-one-out cross-validation; Iso = leave-several-out 10-fold; MCC = Matthews's correlation coefficient; SEN = Sensitivity; SPE = specificity.

#TR	IR _{TS}	#TS	IR _{TS}	Internal Validation						External validation		
				MCC _{loo}	MCC _{Iso}	SEN _{loo}	SEN _{Iso}	SPE _{loo}	SPE _{Iso}	MCC _{EXT}	SEN _{EXT}	SPE _{EXT}
208	4.60	69	4.75	0.40	0.40	0.57	0.56	0.86	0.86	0.39	0.42	0.93

Figure 12. Effect of AD of increasing stringency (*i.e.*, increasing percentage of excluded chemicals) on the predictive performance of the Nrf2 BRF classifier.

1.4.9 QSAR classifier for ER α

The ER α classifier was developed as a function of data associated with the ToxCast endpoint 'ATG_ERa_TRANS_up'. The predictive performance of the ER α classifier is summarized in Table 6. In the absence of an applicability domain, the ER α classifier is characterized by a capacity to detect active chemicals, which is suboptimal and the mechanistic rationale underpinning the modelled *in vitro* test is poorly described by the retained structure-activity relationship. The introduction of an applicability domain (Figure 13) improves external predictivity at the expense of a reduced coverage. At low coverages, the performance of the model could prove to be useful during the screening of list of chemicals since sensitivity reaches 0.7 while specificity is at 0.8 and beyond. As outlined previously, this bias toward high specificities ensures a wise management of experimental resources that will be targeted towards chemicals very likely to be active.

Table 6. Predictive performance on internal and external validation of the ER α BRF classifier; #TR = number of chemicals in training set; #TS = number of chemicals in test set; IR_{TR} = Imbalance Ratio training set (number of inactive chemicals/number of active chemicals); IR_{TS} = Imbalance Ratio training set; loo = leave-one-out cross-validation; Iso = leave-several-out 10-fold; MCC = Matthews's correlation coefficient; SEN = Sensitivity; SPE = specificity.

#TR	IR _{TS}	#TS	IR _{TS}	Internal Validation						External validation		
				MCC _{loo}	MCC _{Iso}	SEN _{loo}	SEN _{Iso}	SPE _{loo}	SPE _{Iso}	MCC _{EXT}	SEN _{EXT}	SPE _{EXT}
208	4.47	69	4.75	0.52	0.53	0.71	0.71	0.86	0.86	0.29	0.42	0.88

Figure 13. Effect of AD of increasing stringency (*i.e.*, increasing percentage of excluded chemicals) on the predictive performance of the ER₂ BRF classifier.

1.4.10 Conclusions on QSAR modeling of iPM(T) chemicals

The results presented in section 1.3 show that the QSAR analysis for iPM(T) chemicals described in the previous paragraphs highlights that data paucity is a major hindrance on the way towards QSAR modeling capable of covering the chemical space spanned by this chemical category and capable of covering several biological endpoints of interest. This hindrance is due to a twofold problem.

The first problem is linked to the paucity of active chemicals and it is a universal problem in the field of toxicology regardless of the property being predicted and it has been described by Zakharov et al. {Zakharov, 2014 #1389}. This problem is then magnified by the scarce availability of list PM chemicals whose definition is based on robust criteria. The overall effect is that few endpoints can be modelled as a function of adequately populated datasets.

An alternative approach to the use of supervised machine learning (relying on labelled data, “active”, vs. “inactive” chemicals) is offered by the opportunity of offering to toxicologists the possibility of inspecting chemical categories as the ones that can be obtained by means of unsupervised learning (e.g. cluster analysis). In the framework of this alternative approach, if deemed appropriate, the experimental activity of “source chemicals” within a cluster can be used to predict by read-across⁷ the biological property of interest of “target chemicals” devoid of experimental information.

⁷ Read-across is a predictive procedure for predicting endpoint information for one or more chemicals (target chemicals), by using data from the same endpoint from chemicals that have been experimentally tested (source chemicals) and that are structurally similar to target chemicals. The assessment of chemical similarity is a complex issue that, in the framework of the REACH regulation, is described by the Read-Across Assessment Framework (RAAF). Mor information available at <https://echa.europa.eu/support/registration/how-to-avoid-unnecessary-testing-on-animals/grouping-of-substances-and-read-across>

2 Set of novel *in vitro* bioassay approaches predicting relevant toxicological endpoints for PFAS/iPM(T) chemicals for QSAR modelling for PFAS

BDS and UBA partnering the practical laboratory testing of effect-based *in vitro* toxicity tests to use a larger panel of tools for predicting relevant toxicological endpoints for PFAS/iPM(T) chemicals. For several non-animal methods (NAMs) such as for the endocrine disrupting modalities both *in vitro* laboratories sharing the same methods such as ER, AR, TR and TTR TR CALUX methods.

2.1 *In vitro* toxicity profiling at BDS

In the first step, twelve out of the 41 PFAS compounds and one technical product (ADONA) have been screened on a wide panel of 12 CALUX bioassays (such as for PPAR, endocrine (EAT) testing, genotoxicity p53 related and general toxicity pathways, e.g., early warning PXR) to characterize them for their *in vitro* toxicity. The most promising bioassays e.g., the TTR TR β CALUX, anti-TR β , PPAR α , anti-PPAR γ , Nrf2 and Cytotox CALUX bioassay were then selected for the remaining 30 PFAS compounds/technical mixture in duplicate.

For the 41 PFAS compounds and one technical product (ADONA) tested on the selected CALUX battery, the TTR-TR β CALUX showed to be the bioassay on which most compounds elicited activities (33 active compounds). Next, the PPAR α CALUX bioassay showed the most activity (21 active compounds), followed by the anti-TR β (17 active compounds), oxidative Nrf2 (11 compounds), anti-PPAR γ (10 active compounds), and cytotox CALUX bioassay (10 compounds). 13 PFAS compounds showed activity above the LOQ in only 3 CALUX bioassays.

Toxicity profiling of these 42 PFAS standards using a tailored set of *in vitro* CALUX bioassays showed that the TTR TR β CALUX bioassay is the most responsive and sensitive bioassay as compared to the other mode of actions evaluated. Figure 1 presents typical dose-response curves using the TTR TR CALUX reporter gene for several PFAS.

Figure 14: Typical concentration-response curves of some selected PFAS by TTR TR β reporter gene CALUX bioanalysis. TTR TR β reporter gene activity is expressed as induction relative to the maximum induction of the PFOA reference series (relative induction RI%).

Table 7: Listing of *in vitro* derived RPF-values of this study and of *in vivo/in silico* read-across derived RPF-values (EU-COM 540, 2022; see also Bil et al. 2021). --- = no activity; na = not analysed.

Reference compound	Bioassay CAS	cytotox CALUX	Nrf2 CALUX	PPARa CALUX	anti-PPARg CALUX	anti-TRb CALUX	TTR-TRb CALUX	EU-COM 540/2022
		TBT 56-36-0	Curcumin 458-37-7	GW7647 265129-71-3	GW9662 22978-25-2	Diclazuril 101831-37-2	PFOA 335-67-1	
Compound	CAS	RPF (-)	RPF (-)	RPF (-)	RPF (-)	RPF (-)	RPF (-)	RPF (-)
Reference compound		2641	196	119849	73907	67	1.0	
PFBA	375-22-4	---	---	2.8	---	---	0.0019	0.05
PFPeA	2706-90-3	---	---	0.63	---	---	0.083	0.03
PFHxA	307-24-4	0.42	---	0.91	---	0.080	0.19	0.01
PFHpA	375-85-9	1.0	---	0.57	0.38	0.25	1.5	0.5
PFOA	335-67-1	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
PFNA	375-95-1	0.91	3.1	0.92	2.3	0.65	0.34	10
PFDcA	335-76-2	1.2	4.9	2.6	---	0.83	0.13	7
PFDoDA	307-55-1	---	---	---	---	0.15	0.025	3
PFBS	375-73-5	---	---	0.17	---	---	0.054	0.001
PFPeS	2706-91-4	---	---	---	---	---	0.082	0.3
PFHxS	355-46-4	0.69	1.0	1.6	---	0.16	1.6	0.6
PFHpS	375-92-8	0.35	2.1	1.4	---	---	1.0	1.3
PFOS	1763-23-1	---	---	0.83	---	---	2.1	2
PFNS	98789-57-2	---	46	0.66	---	---	0.0045	
P37DMOA	172155-07-6	---	5.7	1.6	1.5	0.064	2.3	
ADONA	919005-14-4	---	---	---	---	0.42	0.55	0.03
H4-PFUnDA	34598-33-9	41	---	---	6.6	0.040	0.018	
2:2 FTOH	54949-74-5	---	---	---	---	---	---	
4:2 FTOH	2043-47-2	---	---	---	---	---	0.00030	
6:2 FTOH	647-42-7	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.02
8:2 FTOH	678-39-7	---	48	---	1.9	---	---	0.04
10:2 FTOH	865-86-1	---	---	---	---	---	---	
PFMOPrA	377-73-1	---	---	2.8	---	---	0.0072	
PFPrOPrA	13252-13-6	---	---	---	---	---	0.0035	
PFMOBA	863090-89-5	---	---	2.4	---	---	0.034	
MeFBSA	68298-12-4	---	---	0.65	---	---	0.043	
PFBSA	30334-69-1	---	---	---	---	---	0.011	
HpFHpA	1546-95-8	---	---	1.2	---	---	0.071	
MeFOSA	31506-32-8	---	---	---	---	---	0.015	
EtFOSA	4151-50-2	---	14	---	---	---	0.054	
PFOSA	754-91-6	2.2	---	2.3	2.2	1.1	0.75	
PFMOAA	674-13-5	na	na	na	na	na	0.00044	
N-MeFBSAA	159381-10-9	---	---	0.44	---	---	0.033	
MeFOSAA	2355-31-9	---	---	---	---	---	---	
EtFOSAA	2991-50-6	---	---	---	---	0.17	---	
FOSAA	2806-24-8	---	---	---	---	---	---	
6:2 FTAB	34455-29-3	---	---	---	---	---	0.00015	
6:2 diPAP	57677-95-9	---	---	---	---	0.33	0.0010	
6:2 FTSAM	80475-32-7	---	---	---	---	---	---	
8:2 FTUCA	70887-84-2	---	76	---	10	0.065	0.026	
4:2 FTSA et H4-PFHxS	757124-72-4	---	---	0.21	---	0.047	0.018	
6:2 FTSA et H4-PFOS	27619-97-2	0.00021	1.3	---	2.5	0.15	0.020	0.02

The *in vitro* established relative potency factors (RPF) of the tested PFAS relative to PFOA (RPF = 1) in the TTR TR β CALUX varied between 0.00015 (6:2 FTAB) and 2.3 (P37DMOA). In Table 4, we present the various *in vitro* derived RPF-values obtained from the used CALUX panel as well as the currently in Europe discussed *in vivo/in silico* read-across derived RPFs (EU-COM 540, 2022; see also Bil et al. 2021). The TTR TR CALUX reporter gene assays show relative potencies for most PFAS in the same order of magnitude as the *in vivo* RPFs but differ strongly (up to 5 orders of magnitude) for many other, such as for PFNA to PFDoDA, which may be due to e.g., differences in kinetics. Also, very active thyroid hormone disrupting chemicals such as P37DMOA (RPF = 2.3) and PFOSA (RPF=0.75) are yet lacking from the EU-COM proposal. Now these RPF-values can be used to convert chemical concentrations into PFOA-equivalents (e.g. de Schepper et al. 2024).

The *in vitro* established relative potency factors (RPF) of the tested iPM(T) relative to reference compound of the related CALUX are listed in table 5.

Table 8: Listing of *in vitro* (*non-animal*) derived RPF-values of this study; nd = no activity.

Reference compound CAS	cytotox CALUX TBT 56-36-0	anti-PPAR γ CALUX GW9662 22978-25-2	ER α CALUX 17 β -Estradiol 50-28-2	PXR CALUX Nicardipine 54527-84-3	anti-AR CALUX Flutamide 13311-84-7	TTR-TR β CALUX PFOA 335-67-1	
Compound	CAS	RPF (-)	RPF (-)	RPF (-)	RPF (-)	RPF (-)	
Reference compound		1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	
2-Phenylphenol	90-43-7	0.00030	0.0000068	0.000000058	0.013	0.22	0.0047
3,4-dichloroaniline	95-76-1	0.00028	nd	0.000000022	nd	0.084	0.0041
4,4-Sulfonyldiphenol	80-09-1	0.00025	0.000013	0.0000017	nd	0.0071	0.0052
4-chloroaniline	106-47-8	nd	0.00012	nd	nd	0.067	0.0020
Benzoic acid	65-85-0	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Tri n-butyl phosphate	126-73-8	0.0011	0.000026	nd	0.038	0.017	nd
triphenyl phosphate	115-86-6	0.0034	0.000041	0.00000029	0.10	0.022	nd
1H-Benzotriazol	95-14-7	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
5,6-Dimethyl-1H-benzotriazole	4184-79-6	nd	nd	nd	0.0022	0.0054	nd
5-Chlorobenzotriazole	94-97-3	0.00015	nd	nd	nd	0.0063	0.0057
5-Methyl-1H-benzotriazole	136-85-6	nd	nd	nd	nd	0.0026	0.00048
Benzothiazole	95-16-9	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	0.00029
Benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid	21465-51-0	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	0.00015
Galaxolide	1222-05-5	0.0038	0.000040	0.00000013	0.089	0.69	0.00068
Oxybenzone	131-57-7	0.00026	0.000016	0.00000023	0.011	0.20	nd
Tetrabromobisphenol A	79-94-7	0.0015	0.000065	0.00000015	0.011	0.013	33
Bisphenol A	80-05-7	0.00086	0.000022	0.000020	0.019	0.35	0.0033
4-tert-Octylphenol	140-66-9	0.0065	0.000041	0.00010	0.14	0.73	0.012
1,4-Dioxane	123-91-1	0.00012	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd
Methyl paraben	99-76-3	nd	nd	0.000000057	nd	0.013	0.0025
Triclosan	3380-34-5	0.011	0.00012	nd	0.072	0.64	0.39
1,2,3-benzotriazole	95-14-7	nd	nd	nd	nd	0.0027	nd

2.2 In vitro toxicity profiling at UBA

In a first step, a subset of 12 PFAS and 3 technical products were analysed on a wide panel of bioassays (Table 6). Four modules of toxicological endpoints were used: cytotoxicity (proliferation (RTCA), metabolism (ATP), genotoxicity (formation of micronuclei), oxidative stress (glutathione and formation of ROS) and endocrine activity (receptor binding: estrogenic, anti-androgenic and thyroidal). Based on this first results the biotest battery was further enhanced and the assays for micronuclei and GSH were omitted for the testing of the remaining single substances and the samples from the case studies. The most promising biotests were TTR TR β -CALUX, anti-AR-CALUX and the cytotoxicity module.

Table 9. Results for the first 15 substances. Red: Adverse effect (active); Green: No adverse effect (not active); Yellow: Equivocal effect.

substance	synonyme	Cytotox		Genotox	ox. stress		rezeptor-binding		
		RTCA	ATP	mikro-nuclei	GSH	ROS-DCF	ER-Calux	anti-AR-Calux	TTR-TR-Calux
Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid	PFHxS	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Red	Red
3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-tridecafluorooctane-1-sulfonic acid	6:2 FTSA et H4-PFOS	Red	Red	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Red	Red
Perfluoroheptane sulfonic acid	PFHpS	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
Perfluorooctane sulfonamide	PFOSA	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
perfluorobutanesulfonic acid	PFBS	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
perfluoropentanoic acid	PFPeA	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
perfluorooctanoic acid	PFOA	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
perfluorodecanoic acid	PFDCa / PFDA	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
perfluorobutanoic acid	PFBA	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
perfluoroheptanoic acid	PFHpA	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
perfluorononanoic acid	PFNA	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
perfluorohexanoic acid	PFHxA	Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
Methylparaben		Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
Triclosan		Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red
1H-Benzotriazol		Red	Red	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red

For the further screening of the remaining set of PFAS/technical products and PMTs a bioassay battery consisting of cytotoxicity (RTCA and ATP) and nuclear hormone receptor (anti-AR and TTR-TR β) was selected (table 10 and 11) The tested 44 PFAS showed the most activities in the cytotoxicity module and the TTR-TR β CALUX (35 active compounds in the RTCA, 36 active compounds in the ATP assay and 38 active compounds in the TTR-TR β CALUX). Of the 28 PFAS tested in the anti-AR CALUX, 12 compounds revealed an activity.

The toxicity profiles of these 44 PFAS using the enhanced bioassay battery demonstrated that the TTR-TR β CALUX is the most responsive and sensitive bioassay compared to the other tests. Figure 15 shows typical dose-response curves using the TTR-TR β reporter gene for several PFAS.

Figure 15. Typical concentration-response curves of some selected PFAS by TTR-TR β reporter gene CALUX bioanalysis. TTR-TR β reporter gene activity is expressed as induction relative to the maximum induction of the PFOA reference series (relative induction RI%).

The *in vitro* determined relative potency factors (RPF) of the tested PFAS and PMTs are listed in tables 10 and 11. The relative potency factors (RPF) of the tested PFAS compared to PFOA (RPF = 1) varied between 0.0002 (EtFOSA) and 7.20 (4H-PFUnDA). It is noticeable that the effects of iPM(T) substances are significantly lower than the effects of PFAS with the RPF of triclosan as the highest value (0.0738).

Comparison of the both approaches and conclusions on *In vitro* toxicity profiling We were able to demonstrate that sensitive effect- and human cell-based *in vitro* toxicity based bioanalysis tools can play an important role to assess the *in vitro* toxicity of the selected 45 PFAS, some industrial PFAS products (e.g., ADONA, GenX) and several other PMTs (e.g. benzotriazole, parabens, bisphenol or triclosan). This data shows that the most promising bioassay for the sum of known and unknown PFAS is the TTR TR β CALUX, which is based on their common property to bind to specific thyroid hormone transport proteins and thereby interfering with the thyroid-hormone system with possible adverse health consequences. *In vitro* relative potency factors determined following TTR TR β CALUX bio-analysis of a large set PFAS indicated more relevant not regularly tested PFAS compounds (e.g., P37DMOA). Our studies indicate that not only the now proposed 24 PFAS (EU-COM 540, 2022) show *in vitro* toxic properties but also additional PFAS (PFOSA and P37DMOA) need to be strongly considered. This data indicates that *in vitro* toxicity analysis of yet unknown PFAS using *in vitro* bioassays is a promising and suitable strategy to cover complex mixtures of the handful yet known versus the thousands of yet unknown PFAS.

Table 10. Listing of *in vitro* derived RPF-values for PFAS from the used bioassays; PFOA is the reference substance and set to RPF = 1; nd = no activity; na = not analysed.

Compound	CAS	RTCA RPF (-)	ATP RPF (-)	anti-AR CALUX RPF (-)	TTR-TRb CALUX RPF (-)
PFHxS	355-46-4	0.83	0.21	0.64	0.72
6:2 FTSA et H4-PFOS	27619-97-2	0.53	0.16	nd	0.027
PFHpS	375-92-8	0.95	nd	nd	1.54
PFOSA	754-91-6	nd	3.49	1.94	0.37
PFBS	375-73-5	0.0874	0.033	nd	0.0446
PFPeA	2706-90-3	nd	0.085	nd	0.0198
PFOA	335-67-1	1	1	1	1
PFDCa	335-76-2	1.13	2.01	nd	0.46
PFBA	375-22-4	nd	nd	0.3	0.0024
PFHpA	375-85-9	0.69	0.37	0.57	0.32
PFNA	375-95-1	1.58	2.11	nd	0.39
PFHxA	307-24-4	0.0944	0.12	0.39	0.0614
2:2 FTOH	54949-74-5	nd	nd	nd	nd
4:2 FTSA et H4-PFHxS	757124-72-4	nd	0.79	nd	0.0066
PFMOPrA	377-73-1	nd	nd	nd	0.0007
PFPrOPrA (GenX)	13252-13-6	nd	0.33	nd	0.0015
PFMOBA	863090-89-5	nd	0.12	2	0.0392
MeFBSA	68298-12-4	nd	0.61	2.16	0.0431
PFBSA	30334-69-1	0.35	0.045	nd	0.0122
N-MeFBSAA	159381-10-9	0.3	0.45	nd	0.0245
PFPeS	2706-91-4	0.13	0.1	nd	0.11
P37DMOA	172155-07-6	2.77	6.11	nd	0.93
HPFHpA	1546-95-8	0.15	0.31	0.7	nd
EtFOSA	4151-50-2	1.07	0.4	1.24	0.0002
4:2 FTOH	2043-47-2	nd	nd	nd	0.13
4H-PFUnDA	34598-33-9	7.2	0.39	nd	0.0002
6:2 FTOH	647-42-7	nd	0.12	1.05	nd
8:2 FTOH	678-39-7	2.33	0.56	0.92	nd
GenX	62037-80-3	nd	nd	na	nd
ADONA	919005-14-4	nd	1.06	na	nd
6:2 diPAP	57677-95-9	nd	nd	na	nd
6:2 FTSAM (DPOSA)	80475-32-7	3.61	0.98	na	0.0008
8:2 FTUCA	70887-84-2	1.51	1.63	na	nd
EtFOSAA	2991-50-6	2.72	5.22	na	0.0854
MeFOSAA	2355-31-9	0.63	0.28	na	0.0156
FOSAA	2806-24-8	1.81	3.44	na	nd
PFDoDA	307-55-1	nd	1.04	na	0.0346
MeFOSA	31506-32-8	nd	0.7	na	0.14
PFDS	335-77-3	nd	1.43	na	nd
6:2 FTAB / CDPOS / Capstone B	34455-29-3	1.61	0.0782	na	0.0051
PFNS	98789-57-2	1.57	1.87	na	nd
10:2 FTOH	865-86-1	nd	nd	na	nd
PFOS	1763-23-1	nd	na	na	1.02
PFUnDA	2058-94-8	3.52	na	na	nd

Table 11. Listing of *in vitro* derived RPF-values for iPM(T) from the used bioassays; PFOA is the reference substance and set to RPF = 1; nd = no activity; na = not analysed.

Compound	CAS	RTCA RPF (-)	ATP RPF (-)	anti-AR CALUX RPF (-)	TTR-TRb CALUX RPF (-)
Methyl paraben	99-76-3	0.22	nd	3.81	0.0004
Triclosan	3380-34-5	15.63	4.69	nd	0.0738
1H-Benzotriazol	95-14-7	0.39	nd	0.73	nd
2-Phenylphenol	90-43-7	1.37	na	na	0.012
3,4-dichloroaniline	95-76-1	0.82	na	na	0.0395
4,4'-Sulfonyldiphenol	80-09-1	2.05	na	na	0.0024
4-chloroaniline	106-47-8	0.4	na	na	0.0025
Benzoic acid	65-85-0	nd	na	na	0.0004
Tri n-butyl phosphate	126-73-8	nd	na	na	0.0008
triphenyl phosphate	115-86-6	5.45	na	na	0.0127
5,6-Dimethyl-1H-benzotriazole	4184-79-6	1.91	na	na	nd
5-Chlorobenzotriazole	94-97-3	1.57	na	na	0.0121
5-Methyl-1H-benzotriazole	136-85-6	1.63	na	na	0.0004
Benzothiazole	95-16-9	0.35	na	na	0.0007
Benzothiazole-2-sulfonic acid	21465-51-0	nd	na	na	0.0007
Galaxolide	1222-05-5	10.04	na	na	0.0012
Oxybenzone	131-57-7	1.95	na	na	nd

3. Take home messages

We improved the combination of *in silico* and *in vitro* testing by parallel determinations of a selected panel of around 40 PFAS and 20 PM(T)s to provide a set of toxicological assessment and regulatory tools for the large group of PFAS/PM(T)s.

A set of novel QSAR-grouping and -read-across models and *in vitro* bioassay approaches predicting relevant toxicological endpoints for PFAS/iPM(T) chemicals have been established and applied.

The **in silico modeling** showed from the tested 15 endpoints that most PFAS reflect a high binding probability to sex hormone receptors (TR, anti-AR and ER). However, receptors from the peroxisome proliferator-activated (PPAR α , β , γ) glucocorticoid (GR and anti-GR), liver X (LXR α , β) and retinoid X (RXR α) groups are unaffected or slightly affected by PFAS (low and moderate binding probability).

The *in silico* analyses indicated that the probability of PFAS binding to the receptors depends on the chain length, the number of fluorine atoms, and the number of branches in the molecule.

The **in vitro bioassay analysis** approached for 40 PFAS compounds (e.g. all regulated 20 PFAS) and industrial standards (e.g., ADONA, GenX) with a combination of a wide range of CALUX bioassay endpoints (e.g., table 7 with 6 endpoints) and additional general toxicity *in vitro* bioassays (e.g., table 9 with 8 *in vitro* endpoints) confirmed that sex hormone receptors (TR, anti-AR and ER) and especially the thyroid transport inhibition (TTR TR β) are of main importance for testing of single PFAS compounds and most promising for testing complex mixtures (e.g. water or sediment) of known and unknown PFAS.

Potency factors for selected PFAS/ iPM(T) have been established for several of the used *in vitro* bioassays by two bioassay laboratories (UBA, BDS). Comparing both data sets in case of e.g. TTR TR β CALUX for PFAS showed that in more than 80% of RPF values within an order of magnitude have been found.

Potency factors for selected PFAS have been established for each of the used *in vitro* human cell-based bioassays (named TTR TR β CALUX) ranging for the most active endpoint from the thyroid transport inhibition from non-detected (e.g., several FTOH compounds) to the P37DMOA compound (RPF = up to 2.3; tables 7 and 10).

Additional up to 22 PM(T) chemicals (e.g., table 8 and 10) have been tested with a combination of a wide range of CALUX bioassay endpoints (e.g., table 8 with 6 endpoints) and additional general toxicity *in vitro* bioassays (e.g., table 10 with 4 *in vitro* endpoints). For a toxic-free and Green deal strategy we recommend to use the selected wide range of bioassays (table 8 and 11) to screen the toxic profiles of a set of PM(T) chemicals and their complex mixtures (in soil or water).

Potency factors for selected iPM(T) have been established for each of the used *in vitro* human cell-based bioassays (named CALUX panel) ranging from not-detected (e.g., several *in vitro* endpoints at benzotriazole) up to RPF values above 0.5 for several PMTs (e.g., galaxolide and triclosan, see table 8, or methyl-paraben in table 10 at the male hormone inhibition).

Several different *in vitro* toxicity active (e.g. thyroid hormone transport inhibition) PFAS compounds (e.g. PFOA with RPF = 1; or P37DMOA with RPF = 2.3; or 6:2 FTAB with RPF = 0.00015 in TTR TR β CALUX; see table 7) have been used to find in cluster modelling new structure-analogue compounds.

We **recommend** as next step to further synthesise and analyses these new PFAS by the panel of in vitro toxicity tools here applied on the available data of these 40 plus 2 PFAS standards/industrial mixtures.

Based on this data we **recommend** to use the combination of in silico and in vitro toxicity evaluations of single PFAS congeners from the large group of PFAS as a promising and suitable strategy to cover a large variety of different toxicity endpoints in a time- and cost-efficient way.

Relative potency factors (RPFs) proposed by vitro toxicity tools and can further help to give first toxicity indications for the handful regulated and the not yet regularly tested/regulated PFAS to be included in the testing strategy for single compounds and complex mixtures of these compounds.

The impact of the combination of in silico and vitro toxicity evaluations of single PFAS congeners from the large group of PFAS is a promising and suitable strategy to cover a large variety of different key events in a time- and cost-efficient way.

As a **next step**, the newly proposed active structure-toxicity analogues of PFAS should be further investigated by the proposed in vitro testing battery. Additionally, the **observed differences in RPFs** of a handful PFAS compounds (e.g., PFOS, ADONA or MeFOSA) of both TTR TR CALUX laboratories (BDS, UBA) will be further investigated.

As **preliminary conclusion for policy makers** we would like to add that the indicated in silico tools should be applied for additional PFAS-like compounds (e.g., compounds with CF₂/CF₃ groups) and the in vitro tools as toxic-free testing for safer and sustainable PFAS alternatives for a green environment.

We also would recommend to further focus on the **research gaps** of testing complex mixtures (such as water, sediment and soil) for the sum of known and unknown PFAS and PM(T)s via in vitro toxicity bioequivalents (e.g., PFOA-equivalents/liter water in case of PFAS; estrogen- and flutamide-equivalents/liter water in case of PM(T)s).

Several data and information's have been already presented at several conferences and published as abstracts/full papers in cooperation with all partners. Also the methods/SOPs for the sampling, shipment, extraction and in vitro bioanalysis have been developed and communicated with all partners.

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Annex

Table A1: Initial list of *in silico* and *in vitro* toxicological endpoints used within PROMISCES by BDS, UBA, QSAR Lab and INERIS for selected PFAS and PMTs in the first pre-screening step of the 2-step approach

Number (-)	Cell-based Endpoints (-)	Bioassays methods (BDS; UBA)	QSAR methods (QSARlab; INERIS)
1	Cell death	Cytotox CALUX RTCA, ATP, CDD+, LDH, necrosis PI	x
2	Genotoxicity	P53 CALUX Ames and micronuclei	x
3	Oxidative stress	Nrf2 CALUX ROS detection (DCFHDA, DHE, GHS)	x
4	Estrogenicity (ER)	ER α CALUX	x
5	Androgenicity (AR)		x
6	Inhibition androgenicity (anti-AR)	Anti-AR CALUX	x
7	Progesterone activity (PR)		x
8	Inhibition thyroid hormone activity (anti-TR β)	Anti-TR β CALUX	x
9	Inhibition thyroid hormone transport activity	TTR TR β CALUX	x
10	Inhibition of obesity	Anti-PPAR α CALUX	x
11	Inhibition of obesity	Anti-PPAR γ CALUX	x
12	Mineralocorticoid receptor (MR)		x
13	Early warning	PXR CALUX	x
14	Glucocorticoid receptor (GR)		x
15	Neurotoxicity	MEA	

Table A2: Listing of PFAS compounds (with abbreviation and CAS number) used for in silico modeling and also by in vitro bioanalysis testing (marked in bold)

ID	Abbreviation	CAS	Name
1	10:2FTOH	865-86-1	2-(Perfluorodecyl)ethanol
2	10:2FTUCA	70887-94-4	(Z)-3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,9,9,10,10,11,11,12,12,12-Icosafluoro-2- dodecenoic acid
3	4:2diPAPs	135098-69-0	4:2 Fluorotelomer phosphate diester
4	4:2FTOH	2043-47-2	1-Hexanol, 3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6-nonafluoro-
5	4:2FTS	757124-72-4	1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluorohexanesulphonic acid
6	5:3FTCA	914637-49-3	4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-undecafluorooctanoic acid
7	6:2 Cl-PFESA	756426-58-1	Perfluoro(2-((6-chlorohexyl)oxy)ethanesulfonic acid)
8	6:2FTOH	647-42-7	3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-Tridecafluorooctan-1-ol
9	6:2FTS	27619-97-2	1-Octanesulfonic acid, 3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-tridecafluoro-
10	6:2FTUCA	70887-88-6	3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-dodecafluorooct-2-enoic acid
11	6:2PAPs	57678-01-0	Perfluorooctyl phosphate
12	8:2FTOH	678-39-7	1H,1H,2H,2H-Perfluoro-1-decanol
13	8:2FTS	39108-34-4	3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,9,9,10,10,10-heptadecafluorodecane-1-Sulfonic acid
14	8:2FTUCA	70887-84-2	2H-Perfluoro-2-decenoic acid
15	EtFOSA	4151-50-2	Sulfluramid
16	EtFOSE	1691-99-2	N-ethyl-1,1,2,2,3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-heptadecafluoro-N-(2-hydroxyethyl)octane-1-sulfonamide
17	PFOSA	754-91-6	Perfluorooctanesulfonamide
18	MeFOSA	31506-32-8	Heptadecafluoro-N-methyloctanesulphonamide
19	MeFOSE	24448-09-7	N-Methylperfluorooctanesulfonamidoethanol
20	Mhopflca n=6	no	6:1 Fluorotelomer ether acetate
21	Mhopflca n=7	no	7:1 Fluorotelomer ether acetate
22	Mhopflca n=8	no	8:1 Fluorotelomer ether acetate
23	PFBA	375-22-4	Heptafluorobutyric acid
24	PFBS	375-73-5	Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid
25	PFCHS	2106-55-0	Perfluorocyclohexane sulfonic acid
26	PFDA	335-76-2	Perfluorodecanoic acid
27	PFEtS	354-88-1	Pentafluoroethanesulfonic acid
28	PFHpA	375-85-9	Perfluoroheptanoic acid
29	PFHpS	375-92-8	Perfluoroheptanesulfonic acid
30	PFHxA	307-24-4	Perfluorohexanoic acid
31	PFHxPA	40143-76-8	Perfluorohexylphosphonic acid
32	PFHxS	355-46-4	Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid
33	PFNA	375-95-1	Perfluorononanoic acid
34	PFNS	68259-12-1	Perfluorononanesulfonic acid
35	PFOA	335-67-1	Perfluorooctanoic acid
36	PFOPA	40143-78-0	(Heptadecafluorooctyl)phosphonic acid
37	PFOS	1763-23-1	Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid
38	PFPeA	2706-90-3	Perfluoropentanoic acid
39	PFPeS	2706-91-4	Perfluoropentanesulfonic acid
40	PFPrA	422-64-0	Pentafluoropropionic acid
41	PFPrS	110676-15-8	Perfluoropropane sulfonate
42	PFUdA	2058-94-8	Perfluoroundecanoic acid
43	TFA	76-05-1	Trifluoroacetic acid